

Relative Reactivities of Aromatic (C-H) and Aromatic (C-Si) Bonds

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Relative reactivities of aromatic (C-H) and aromatic (C-Si) bonds towards electrophilic acetylations have been studied by competition technique, using g.l.c. as the analytical tool. The limitations of the competition method to study such reactivities have been discussed.

It has been reported that the acid-catalyzed solvolytic cleavage of aryl-silicon bonds in compounds of the type Ar.SiR_3 (Ar = aromatic; and R = alkyl group) is an electrophilic substitution in which a proton, initially solvated, is the attacking species¹⁻³. Eaborn and co-workers have studied extensively the mechanism of protodesilylations and also the substituent effects⁴⁻¹¹. Besides protodesilylation, various other electrophils have been used to study the mechanism of the desilylation reactions^{9,12-14}. During the course of our investigation on the acyl-desilylations¹⁵⁻¹⁸, it has been observed that the success of the acyl-desilylations leading to ketone monomers (or, polymers) depends upon the greater reactivity of aryl-silicon bond compared with the aryl-hydrogen bond, and very mild reaction conditions are sufficient for such electrophilic carbon-silicon bond cleavage by acyl-carbonium ions under Friedel-Crafts reaction conditions. An attempt has, therefore, been made to obtain a semi-quantitative measure of this difference in reactivity by a competition method using gas liquid chromatography as an analytical tool.

EXPERIMENTAL

Solvents and chemicals were purified and dried by usual procedures.

The products were analyzed by gas liquid chromatography (g.l.c.) using 5.5% PEG 1540 column and nitrogen (50 ml. min.⁻¹) as the carrier gas. Chart rate was 20 inch. hr.⁻¹ at 150°. Ratio between the products formed was calculated from peak-heights by usual technique. Results are shown in tabular form below.

Phenyltrimethylsilane, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Si}(\text{CH}_3)_3$ was prepared by the published method of Freiser, *et al.*¹⁹, b.p. 169°-170°/758 mm, n_D^{25} 1.4883.

In a typical reaction, known amounts of phenyltrimethylsilane and toluene were allowed to compete for a deficiency of acetyl chloride under Friedel-Crafts condition, e.g. Acetylchloride (3.16 g; 0.04 mole) in CS_2 (20 ml) was added dropwise during 20 mins. to a well-stirred ice-cold mixture of toluene (5.53 g; 0.06 mole), phenyltrimethylsilane (9.0 g; 0.06 mole) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (6.65 g; 0.05 mole) in CS_2 (50 ml.). The reaction mixture was stirred for half an hour at 0°, then refluxed gently for 2 hrs., and finally

hydrogen chloride cleavage of phenyl-silicon bond is appreciable, the amounts of phenyltrimethylsilane competing with toluene will slowly decrease as the reaction proceeds. All these facts would lend to reduce the accuracy of the present result, but it can be said from the present results that phenyl-silicon bond in phenyltrimethylsilane is at least three times as reactive as the para-position of toluene; and since it is known²³ that under comparable conditions toluene is about 100 times more reactive than benzene it may be assumed that the aryl-silicon bond in phenyltrimethylsilane is about 1800 times more reactive than benzene towards Friedel-Crafts acylation. The preparative usefulness of this enhanced reactivity of phenyl-silicon bond over phenyl-hydrogen bond has been discussed elsewhere¹⁵⁻¹⁸.

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